

ENVIRONMENTAL MICROBIOLOGY: HOW MICROBES IMPACT ECOSYSTEMS AND CLIMATE CHANGE

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ABSTRACT

Soil microorganisms are microscopic organisms that live inside the soil. They perform various vital functions while residing inside the soil. One of the important functions of soil microbes is the cycling of nutrients like carbon and nitrogen. Climate change becoming a threat to the living organisms on this planet. The soil microbes can effectively manage the impact of climate change. They make a balance of carbon and nitrogen between the soil and the atmosphere. They are also known as the guardians of the earth because they protect soil from degradation. They increase the fertility of the soil by degrading organic compounds inside the soil. Because of this property, these microbes are important for the enhancement of plant growth as they increase nutrient uptake by plants, provide nitrogen to the plant from the atmosphere via the process of nitrogen fixation and they produce some chemicals that act as plant growth-promoting substances. With a better understanding of soil microbes, we can enhance soil health, soil productivity, and water retention capacity of soil, and we can also increase crop yield with the use of these microbes. These microbes can be utilized for a cleaner environment because of their biodegradation, bioremediation, and phytoremediation roles in our environment. However, the problem is that climate change badly impacts the soil microbes and changes their optimal composition. Data-driven technologies can be utilized to enhance the growth of soil microbes and to mitigate the impact of climate change, sustainable agriculture, and a cleaner/safer ecosystem in the future.

Keywords: Carbon sequestration, Climate change, Ecosystems, Nutrient cycling, Soil microbes

INTRODUCTION

Climate change is a widely accepted threat to humans and other living organisms on this planet. A report published by the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) indicated that the situation is becoming more adverse with the passing year, more than 3.3 billion world's population is directly threatened by climate change around the globe. Unsustainable development all over the world gives a boost to

climate change and produces hazardous chemicals (CHANGE, 2007). Environment and climate change may alter the production of various gasses like methane including many harmful gasses. The atmospheric concentration of many gases like CO₂, NH₄, and N₂O has increased recently upto 40, 150, and 20% respectively, as a result of climate change. The emission of these gases further makes life difficult on this earth (Danovaro et al.,

2017). Climate change not only impacts air quality but is also responsible for heat stress, raised sea levels, extreme weather events, food and water security, and population migration. These types of changes in climate cause various diseases like diarrhea, malnutrition, cardiovascular, respirators, vector diseases, and infections. Other effects of climate change are economic instability, loss of homes, forced migration, *etc.* (Kim et al., 2014). Soil microbes can be a novel solution to combat climate change's impact on this planet. The soil microbes play a crucial role in balancing the carbon cycle across the globe which results in reduced greenhouse gasses in the atmosphere. The soil microbes also help to regulate the nutrient cycle on the earth like nitrogen, carbon, methane, *etc.*, and stabilize soil structure which mitigates the impact of climate change (Wu et al., 2024). This literature review aims to summarize the impact of climate change on our earth and soil microbes. Further, this review aims to explore the role of soil microbes to mitigate the impact of climate change and improve soil health and productivity.

Climate change impact on soil microbes

Climate change directly impacts the soil microbial community and its functions. Changes in carbon and nitrogen cycles in soil affect climate change via positive feedback to the atmosphere like greenhouse gas emissions and through negative feedback like carbon immobilization on microbial/plant communities. Understanding soil microbe's interactions with climate change will help us to improve climate. However, climate change imposes many negative effects on soil microbes (Padhy et al., 2020). Recently, many factors have been reported to interfere with climate change and soil microbial community.

Soil warning

Climate monitoring systems are predicting upto 3.7 °C by 2100. This change will lead to an unavoidable impact on the microbial community of the soil. Soil warning may induce step-wise change in soil microbial communities. First of all, soil warning will increase the rate of organic carbon decomposition by providing optimal temperatures for soil bacteria, ultimately

increasing bacterial biomass. Already, an increase of upto 150% in the microbial population in the soil has been reported from the parts where global warming is a major issue. The increased organic carbon decomposition will lead to carbon depletion which will result in the decline of microbial population. Changes have been observed in the microbial population, community, physiologies, and functional profiles because microbes adapt to warming and their metabolism tries to adjust according to traces of carbon in soil. Some studies have reported that global warming is associated with increased microbial community diversity and richness. Phylum actinobacteria acidobacteria and class alphaproteobacterial are prominent bacteria in soil affected by warming as reported by (Fu et al., 2023). These bacterial phylum changes occurred because oligotrophic taxa *i.e.*, slow-growing bacteria that require low nutrients are promoted like actinobacteria over copiotrophic taxa like fast-growing bacteria which require a nutrient-rich environment like Bacteroidetes. Consequently, changing soil composition. Warming treatments for upto 8 years showed favorable conditions for recalcitrant carbon degrading taxa (actinobacteria and acidobacteria) while discouraging the growth of copiotrophic taxa as reported by (Grant et al., 2022). Considerable differences in ammonia oxidation have also been observed following soil microbiology.

Global warming affects microbial functions, directly by accelerating enzymatic functions and indirectly by changing soil properties. For instance, warming has accelerated phosphorus and sulfur cycles nitrogen cycle has been reported to be influenced by warming including nitrification, denitrific nitrogen fixation, and nitrogen mineralization (Chaudhary et al., 2023). With the increase in global warming, the pool size of soil inorganic nitrogen and plant nitrogen increases which decreases the rate of nitrogen cycle and microbial decomposition. On the other side, carbon cycling seems to be accelerated by global warming but depends on organic carbon availability. The increased temperature provides optimal temperature to the carbon degrading enzymes but the process is slowed down with time, as most of the carbon degraded within a

short period. After that, only a few genes are involved to decompose traces of carbon. Carbon cycling also depends on the layers of the soil, because organic and mineral composition behave differently after temperature changes. Soil warming is not the only factor that impacts climate change but many different approaches also contribute (Moinet et al., 2020).

Elevated carbon dioxide

Warming is also responsible for elevated carbon dioxide (eCO₂) which has affected soil microbes directly or indirectly. The eCO₂ increases microbial biomass, respiration rates, and genetic signals for carbon cycling processes. Enhanced plant production and rhizodeposition are also associated with eCO₂ but it is all for short terms. In the long term, the eCO₂ disturbs taxonomic trends of soil microbes and even leads to depletion of some of the bacterial genera like Acidobacteria (Yu et al., 2018). A decrease in copiotrophic Bacteroidetes and an increase in microbes with lower RNA was observed following 14 years of eCO₂ in California grassland. Further, eCO₂ is expected to enhance oligotrophic microbes because of the depletion of carbon and soil moisture. On the other side, eCO₂ is expected to stimulate bacterial and plant growth,

which will deplete soil nitrogen and will negatively affect soil carbon cycling. These conditions will prefer the growth of slow-growing microbes while inhibiting the growth of fast-growing microbes which require a nutrient-rich environment (Jin et al., 2022).

Impact on plant microbes

Plant species tend to migrate towards high altitudes and elevations with the increase in global warming. They produce flowers and leaves earlier than their time and also change functional trait's expression (Aubin et al., 2016). Shrubification has resulted in arctic regions because of warming as grasses and forbs have been replaced by woody shrubs, resulting in changes in the overall ecosystem (Mekonnen et al., 2021). Microbial communities that are associated with plants might facilitate or retard this plant transition. For instance, microbial communities that are associated with plant roots strongly influence plant growth, physiology, and gene expression and all of these genes respond to climate change (Aqeel et al., 2023). The consequences of plant-microbe interactions and climate change on the functions of ecosystems are still under discussion (Wahid et al., 2020).

Figure 1 The figure shows the direct effect of climate change on carbon feedback in an ecosystem

Large-scale soil microbiome change induced by climate might impact plant growth and soil carbon balance in the long run (Figure 1). Change in soil microbial communities because of climate change will determine the plant species' success and growth. These changes will result in adverse effects on the ecosystem. Recently a study reported that soil microbial communities protect plants from drought stress (Lau & Lennon, 2012). Similarly, Lau and Lennon (2012) reported that changes in microbial diversity directly impact the functional traits of plants. The difference between the direct and indirect impact of climate change on plants and associated microbial communities can differ significantly. D reported a significant difference in microbial communities of soil samples collected from the low precipitated areas and plant nearby areas. This difference indicates that ecosystems will be affected badly if plant species adapt to shift towards high altitudes because of climate change. The effect of strong interactions among soil microbial species and plants might impact soil systems and ecosystem functions like carbon cycle and trajectory over

time. Further experiments should be conducted to explore the effect of these plant microbe's interactions on the ecosystem.

Warming effects on plant fungi interactions

Global warming has been reported to affect beneficial associations between plants and endophytic fungi (Yan et al., 2019). An increase in temperature has been associated with fluctuations in the occurrence of endophytic fungi in plant tissues (Fang et al., 2019). However, Nouh and Abdel-Azeem (2025) reported that the occurrence of pathogenic endophytic fungi *N. coenophialum* in *S. phoenix* was not disturbed by warming. Similarly, Masumoto (2019) reported that an increase in the density of different fungal genotypes was observed inside the root section of *Salix arctica* in the Canadian high arctic tundra site by warming but no change was observed in the richness and composition of the community. This indicates that any increase in temperature is not directly associated with changes in endophytic communities but it impacts plant species diversity which led to changes in endophytic fungal communities.

Climate change impact on genomic data

With the advancements in sequencing technologies, species diversity of microbial communities in soil and the impact of warming on diversity can be determined. Research must be conducted on multi-omics approaches and the development of cutting-edge tools for communication between soil microbes affected by warming and soil respiration. In Figure 2, stages of many chemical reactions are described on one side while on the other side, various microbial cells are shown by colors. Soil microbiome help us understand the key questions related to climate change (Jansson & Hofmockel, 2020). They used

to investigate the impact of climate change by reducing greenhouse gas emissions, promoting carbon sequestration, and improving soil health and plant growth. We can have a sustainable and better future by using the capabilities of these microbes. Although microbial research on climate change is providing sufficient findings, still there is a need to learn the mutual interactions between plants, microbes, and the environment (Singh Yadav et al., 2023). Further research in the future will help us understand these complex interactions and enhance our ability to use these microbes to manage the changes to climate change effectively.

Figure 2 the figure showed the microbial potential during various environmental variables

Use of microbes to improve soil quality

Interactions between soil, plants, and atmosphere form a complex system that regulates the climate on this planet. Soil microbes play an important role in maintaining these interactions. Climate change impact can be minimized by using microorganisms for our benefit and natural ecosystem. Few ways to use microbes for a better climate are discussed in this article.

In carbon sequestration

Carbon sequestration is a phenomenon in which atmospheric carbon dioxide is captured and stored in soil organic matter. Climate change issues can be addressed by soil microbes very effectively. Soil microbes form humus-like substances from the organic matter and stabilize it by producing glues like glomalin. Thus, helps protect the organic matter from further decomposition and makes it recalcitrant (Rodrigues et al., 2023). Similarly, these microbes help us manage climate change issues by storing maximum carbon in the soil and reducing carbon from the atmosphere (Ahmed & McKay, 2024). Stable carbon compounds made by soil microbes, especially

fungi, improve plant growth by providing more organic matter to the plant roots (Xueling Wang et al., 2024a).

In nutrient cycle

Soil microbes greatly influence the cycling of nutrients in terrestrial ecosystems. They also increase the nutrient availability to the plants by breaking down organic matter, nutrient mineralization, and by developing symbiotic connections with plants (Jacoby et al., 2017). For example, the symbiotic relationship between plants and mycorrhizal fungi enhances nutrient uptake by the plant. Similarly, some symbiotic bacteria perform nitrogen fixation by taking nitrogen from the atmosphere and converting it into usable nitrogen by plants. These activities of microbes not only support plant growth but also preserve soil fertility. Therefore, nutrient cycling in soil is not possible without soil microbes (Wahab et al., 2023). They further support plant growth and productivity by breaking down organic matter into nutrients that can be utilized by plants. Ultimately, these microbial activities reduce carbon dioxide levels in the atmosphere.

In soil health

Soil microbes play a vital role in preserving soil health by performing several essential tasks. They actively convert complex substances into usable nutrients by breakdown of organic content. During the process of organic matter breakdown, they produce some mucus-like substances like glomalin which play a role in soil stability and help in improving overall soil structure (Wei et al., 2024). Similarly, some microorganisms work as factories of bioactive metabolite that inhibit the growth of pathogens and thus, they control disease outbreaks in soil. Enhanced crop production and availability of fertile soil will not be possible without the role of soil microorganisms. Their metabolic systems work to detoxify contaminants and control the pH of soil (Saeed et al., 2021a). A stable microbe community is essential for a stable and fertile ecosystem. The soil microbes also work as important soil health markers (Schloter et al., 2018). Healthy soil results in better plant growth and reduced atmospheric carbon dioxide.

Therefore, good research knowledge is required to reduce the impact of climate change on our ecosystem and for sustainable agriculture and a healthy environment.

In methane emission

In addition to carbon dioxide, microbes play an important role in the emission of methane. Methane is one of the important greenhouse gases and its regulation by soil microbes can significantly impact greenhouse gas dynamics. One of the major portions of methane gas is regulated by methanogenic bacteria that convert methane gas into carbon dioxide. Thus, methane cycling also regulates atmospheric carbon dioxide (Bastviken et al., 2023).

In water retention

Microbes also play an important role in the process of water retention which is the property of soil. They enhance soil structure by forming aggregates which ultimately improve the water-holding capacity of soil (X. Wang et al., 2024). They further keep intact soil particles by producing exudates like polysaccharides and proteins (Chauhan et al., 2023). Furthermore, biogeochemical processes are also influenced by soil microbes which also improve the water retention capacity of soil. For instance, soil organic matter is decomposed by microbes, and nutrients released can be used by plants which enhances water uptake by plants. Hydraulic properties like hydraulic conductivity are also affected by soil microbes which improve water movements through soil (Xueling Wang et al., 2024b). Microbes decompose organic matter within the soil and this process releases water present in the organic matter. This property is important to regulate water in soil especially in dry environments (Rabbi et al., 2024).

In enhancing plant growth and development

Climate change impact can be minimized with the help of microbes as they improve plant growth and development by providing useable nutrients to the plant. The growth of the plant will use maximum carbon dioxide from the atmosphere which will result in lower carbon dioxide levels in the atmosphere (Fiodor et al., 2021). Soil

microbes not only facilitate nutrient uptake by plants but also inhibit the pathogenic microbes and their pathogenicity. They also facilitate the production of growth-promoting substances. Soil microbes like fungi, rhizobia, and plant growth-promoting bacteria develop symbiotic relationships with plants to perform these vital functions (Saeed et al., 2021b). Mutualistic symbionts like mycorrhizal fungi are often reported to form beneficial associations with the roots of plants. These fungal associations increase the surface area of roots which enhances nutrient uptake by the plants. They also solubilize nutrients in the soil by releasing organic acid (Khaliq et al., 2022). In return, they get carbohydrates from the plants. Some soil bacteria like rhizobia form nitrogen-fixing associations with legume plants. They increase nitrogen availability to the plant by converting atmospheric nitrogen into nitrogen that can be used by plants which results in improved growth (Fahde et al., 2023). Some diverse groups of bacteria like plant growth-promoting bacteria, colonize the plant roots and enhance growth via different mechanisms. They produce some hormones that function to promote root growth. They also produce some antimicrobials to protect plants from pathogens and solubilize nutrients to promote plant growth (Saeed et al., 2021b).

In polluted environment

Soil microbes in contaminated soil can detoxify hazardous pollutants. A few mechanisms, to detoxify hazardous pollutants are discussed below. **Biodegradation:** Hazardous heavy metals and organic pollutants can be detoxified by soil microbes (Karnwal et al., 2024). Biodegradation involves specific microbial enzymes that have the ability that degrade toxic pollutants. In this process, microbes can completely degrade a toxic pollutant or convert it into a less toxic pollutant

(Karigar & Rao, 2011). **Bioremediation:** The ability of soil microbes can be utilized to break down and minimize their potentially hazardous effects by detoxification (Ayilara & Babalola, 2023). Some hazardous heavy metals like mercury, cadmium, and lead can be detoxified and removed from the contaminated soil. Bioremediation is a process in which heavy metals can be transformed/volatilized, or immobilized using microorganisms (Igiri et al., 2018). **Phytoremediation:** Some plants have the ability to detoxify and reduce the risks of heavy metals from the soil. They effectively mitigate the harmful effects of hazardous heavy metals (Bhat et al., 2022). These plants accumulate heavy metals in their tissues and microbes associated with these plants work to break down/detoxify the harmful substances. Phytoremediation is an emerging technique that can be applied to mitigate various contaminants across the globe in an environmentally friendly manner (Bhat et al., 2022).

In stress management

Climate change badly affects wild plant species. Beneficial microbes like plant growth-promoting bacteria and some fungi can help plants combat the adverse effects of climate change by providing maximum nutrients and optimizing plant growth (Li et al., 2024). The plant growth-promoting bacteria can be applied directly to the plants/crops in the form of granular or liquid probiotics and seed coatings. These microbes already have been used for nitrogen fixation in legume plants (Lobo et al., 2019). Scientists are now interested in harnessing plant growth-promoting bacteria to manage the impact of climate change while utilizing them as biofertilizers and biopesticides. Researchers are working on plant-promoting bacteria to enhance them to cope with plant drought stress (Li et al., 2024) (Table 1).

Table-1. The table represent various microbes and their role in our ecosystem

Sr No.	Soil Microbes	Roles
1	Nitrogen-fixing Bacteria	Enhance nitrogen availability in soil, improving soil health and plant growth, which boosts biomass and carbon storage.
2	Fungi	Contribute to the formation of stable carbon compounds, aiding carbon sequestration in the soil.
3	Arbuscular Mycorrhizal	Enhance nutrient uptake and plant growth, reducing the need for

	Fungi	synthetic fertilizers.
4	Methanotrophic Bacteria	Oxidize methane, thereby reducing methane emissions from the soil
5	Cyanobacteria	Fix atmospheric nitrogen and enhance soil organic matter, contributing to carbon storage.
6	Actinobacteria	Decompose organic material and promote soil health, leading to greater carbon sequestration.
7	Phosphate-Solubilizing Bacteria	Facilitate phosphorus uptake in plants, reducing reliance on chemical fertilizers.
8	Denitrifying Bacteria	Convert nitrate into nitrogen gas, mitigating nitrous oxide emissions
9	Vesicular-Arbuscular Mycorrhizal (VAM) Fungi	Improve nutrient absorption and plant growth, enhancing carbon storage while decreasing fertilizer usage.
10	Cellulose-Degrading Bacteria	Break down plant residues, enhancing soil health and promoting carbon sequestration.
11	Acetogenic Bacteria	Convert CO ₂ into acetate, contributing to lower greenhouse gas emissions
12	Sulfur-Oxidizing Bacteria	Oxidize sulfur compounds, helping to reduce soil acidification and boost plant productivity.
13	Azotobacter	Fix atmospheric nitrogen and promote plant growth, reducing dependence on synthetic fertilizers.
14	Methanogens	Convert CO ₂ into methane, reducing overall carbon emissions in specific ecosystems.
15	Actinomycetes	Produce antibiotics and enhance soil health, aiding in carbon sequestration.
16	Nitrifying Bacteria	Convert ammonium to nitrate, reducing the release of nitrous oxide
17	Lactic Acid Bacteria	Enhance soil structure and nutrient cycling, promoting carbon sequestration.
18	<i>Bacillus subtilis</i>	Suppresses plant pathogens and stimulates plant growth, reducing the need for chemical pesticides and fertilizers

CONCLUSION

This literature review aims to summarize the climate change impact on our ecosystem and soil especially. In this paper, we discussed how the change in climate affects the microbiome of our earth and the consequences of these changes. Many studies have reported that with the effective use of soil microorganisms, we can minimize the impact of climate change. Soil microbes have the ability to effectively manage the changing conditions. They can play a role in soil destruction management, and plant productivity by providing nutrients to the plants. The soil microbes can also work as regulators and cyclers of many nutrients in between soil and atmosphere. By studying soil microbes in depth, we can use microbes in various processes like enhanced plant health and plant

growth, protection of plants from plant pathogens, etc.

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